

Influence of Infrastructural Facilities on Academic Performance among Government Secondary School Students in Dutsin-ma Local Government Area, Katsina State

Busa, Abdul'aziz Inusa¹

abdulazizbusa@gmail.com

08067574620

Shamsudeen, Salisu¹

sshamsuddeen1@fudutsinma.edu.ng

08130033723/08085598850

Nnamdi, Sunday E.¹

nnamdisunday31@gmail.com

08031127420/08080142894

¹Department of Educational Administration and Planning, Federal University of Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Abstract

The study investigated the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-ma, Dutsin-ma LGA, Katsina State. A Cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of 2376 (male 1234 and female 1142) students of government junior secondary school class two (JSS11) during the 2023/2024 academic session in Dutsin-MA local government area of Katsina State. A sample size of 146 (Male 86 and female 60) Students were selected from the target population using stratified sampling technique as the respondents. Three research questions and one hypothesis were used to elucidate information from the respondents. Self-structured questionnaire was used to generate information from the respondents. The instrument was validated by two experts from Educational Administration and Planning and the other from Educational Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was 0.76. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level using Chi-square statistics. The findings of the study revealed that school facilities influence students' academic performance. The study concluded that there is a Positive and significant relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma, Dutsin-Ma LGA Katsina State. It therefore recommends among others, that the government should make available all the necessary school facilities to enhance teaching and learning as well as students' academic performance.

Keywords: School facilities, infrastructural facilities, instructional materials.

Introduction

This study is to examine the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-MA local government area of Katsina State. Education is a fundamental pillar in the development of any society, serving as a catalyst for individual growth, social progress, and economic advancement. Nigeria, like many other developing nations is faced with various challenges in its education sector. While efforts are being made to improve access to education, most concerned stakeholders in education still advocated for increase in the quality of education provided. One crucial aspect influencing the quality of education is the state of schools and its facilities. The adequacy and functionality of these facilities play significant roles in shaping the learning experiences and consequently, students' academic performance.

School facilities are materials used directly or indirectly for the benefit of influencing teaching and learning in education. They are described entirely as the school plant and examples are the school classroom blocks, staffrooms and offices, laboratories, workshops, libraries, laboratories equipment, consumables, audio-visual aids, electricity, water, chairs, tables, stationeries, playground, storage spaces and others which school has (Sabitu, Babatunde, & Oluwole, 2012). Osaigbovo & Osaigbovo, (2021) also referred to school facilities as the school site, the buildings, the playgrounds, the equipment and other material resources provided in the school for effective teaching and learning operations. They continued by referring to School

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facilities as that comprising the location, weather, lighting, ventilation, floor, space per pupil, health, and safety conditions, play areas, cafeteria and library.

Recognizing the pivotal role of education, nations worldwide invest substantial resources in developing and maintaining an effective educational system. An integral component of this system is the physical infrastructure of schools, encompassing classrooms, libraries, laboratories, recreational areas, and other facilities that collectively contribute to the overall learning environment. According to Bimler (2009), infrastructural school facilities includes; buildings such as administrative block, (which comprises, the principal's office, vice principal and staff rooms, classroom) laboratory, sick bay, music room, typing pool, school gymnasium, cafeteria, security post, school farm, sport field, school shop, storage house, computer room, language laboratory, constant water supply and more. Dusabemariya, Andala and Ochig. (2020) opined that the purpose of teaching aids is to facilitate meaningful communication between the teacher and the teacher. They are intended to make learning process more engaging and interactive, and to help learners better understand and retain information.

According to Dusabemariya et al., (2020) teaching aids play a great role in enlightening the learners' academic performance in classroom. This is because of the increasing participation and involvement due to the motivational effect created on the teachers and learners in classroom setting. Ngirabakunzi (2017) opined that teaching aids are usually perceived to be motivational materials and deliver enthusiasm in lesson, and that real use of teaching aids results into an interesting learning situation. The use of graphics including charts, posters, sketches, cartoons, graphs and drawings, graphics, communicate facts and ideas clearly through combination of drawings, words and pictures.

In the context of junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria, examining the influence of school facilities on students' academic performance becomes imperative. Dutsin-Ma, situated in the northern part of the country, represents a microcosm of the larger educational landscape in Nigeria. Understanding the dynamics between school infrastructure and academic outcomes in this specific region is crucial for designing targeted policy reforms and interventions. There is a growing body of research that suggests a strong relationship between school facilities and students' academic performance. Adequate and well-maintained facilities have been associated with positive learning experiences, enhanced teacher-student interactions, and improved overall educational outcomes. Conversely, deficiencies in infrastructure may hinder the teaching-learning process, impeding students' ability to reach their full academics potentials. Inadequate facilities will surely affect the smooth teaching and learning process in all schools. The major factor that seems to contribute to poor academic performance is inadequate provision of educational facilities in schools. Akhiehiero (2011) posited that educational curriculum cannot be sound and well operated with poor and badly managed school facilities, most especially the physical resources that facilitate effective teaching and learning process. These included classrooms blocks, laboratories, workshops, libraries, equipment, consumables, electricity and water among others. Various dimensions of school facilities need adequate and urgent examination. These encompass the physical condition of classrooms, availability of libraries and laboratories, access to modern technology, and the overall safety and hygiene of the school environment. Understanding how these factors interplay in the specific context of Dutsin-Ma will shed light on the unique challenges and opportunities faced by student in the area. Moreover, the socio-economic context of Katsina State, coupled with the prevailing educational policies, adds layers of complexity to the relationship between school facilities and academic performance. Economic disparities, cultural factors, and government initiatives all contribute to the educational landscape, shaping the experiences of students in junior secondary schools.

As stakeholders continue to advocate for educational reforms in Nigeria, this study aims to contribute valuable insights into the nuanced relationship between school facilities and students' academic performance in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. By doing so, it seeks to inform policymakers, educators, and community leaders, paving the way for evidence-based interventions that can enhance the educational journey and future prospects of students in the study.

There has been so much outcry about the academic performance among junior secondary school students in Dutsin-MA Local Government Area of Katsina State, State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB, 2023). This problem may have originated from poor and inadequate school facilities in the schools. Some of the identified problems include poor infrastructural facilities, such as; administrative block, inadequate classrooms, laboratories, computer laboratories and its accessories and school gymnasium. Also identified are lack or inadequate instructional facilities such as teaching materials, laboratory equipment, television, projectors cardboard, science practical facilities, pictures, maps and the rest. Improper school physical environment, such as school playground, sport field and equipment, agricultural farm for practical and school bus and the rest (Ngirabaunzi, 2017).

Inadequate school facilities affects teaching and learning processes in school. This is because of the large class size. It is a known fact therefore that students' academic performance depend purely on their level of exposure to the learning facilities within the school environment, (Oasigbovo & Oasigbovo, 2021). In this case, the classroom condition, like

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overcrowding, noise, few desk, lack of ceiling fans, appropriate doors and windows for ventilation and the aesthetic condition of the school, making teaching and learning uncondusive within the environment. Irrespective of the fact that some of these facilities are available in some schools like the Government Pilot junior secondary school, in Dutsin-MA, the expectation was that these facilities should be enough and effectively used for teaching and learning, but the reverse is the case in Government Pilot junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma LGA.

This has also brought lack of interest in the practical/demonstration activities on various subjects by the students and has also resulted to their poor academic performance and failure. This is the reason why the authors decided to examine the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-ma Local Government Area, Katsina State

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to the influence of infrastructural facilities on academic performance among government secondary school students in Dutsin-ma local government area, katsina state. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. Examine the influence of infrastructural facilities on Academic performance of government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA
2. Examine the influence of instructional facilities on Academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA
3. Identify factors affecting management of school facilities and academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA

Research Question

1. What is the influence of infrastructural facilities on Academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?
2. What are the instructional facilities influence Students' Academic performance of government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?
3. What are the factors influencing the management of school facilities in government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma LGA?

Research Hypothesis

1. H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance of government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma LGA.

Methodology

A Cross sectional survey research design was used for this study. The population for the study consists of 2376 (*male 1234 and female 1142*) Junior Secondary School (JSS) Students in Dutsin-ma LGA, Katsina state. A sample size of 146 (Male 86 and female 60) Students were selected from the target population using stratified sampling technique as the respondents. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Influence of School Facilities on Student Academic Performance Questionnaire" (ISFSAPQ). The questionnaire was made up of two sections; Section A and Section B. Section A consists of the respondents' demographic data, while section B consists of fifteen (15) items based on the research questions. The questionnaire items were structured using Four (4) Likert point scale of Strongly Agree (SA) 4, Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) 2, Strongly and Disagree (SD) 1 scales of measurement. Self-structured questionnaire was administered directly to the respondents face to face with the help of some teachers, and this was done to ensure that at least 99% of the questionnaire items was returned. Weighted mean was used in the study as a method of data analysis. A criterion mean of 2.5 is used to judge the mean response from the respondents. Mean response above 2.5 cut-off level is accepted and mean response below 2.5 cut off-level is rejected.

Results

The descriptive socio-demographic characteristics of the sample are presented in

Figure 1: Sex Distribution of the Respondent (Source: Fieldwork 2024)

This is because in the northern Nigeria only male gender were given much privilege to attend school while female gender was encouraged to go into marriage the at the younger age Figure1.

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Figure 2: Age Distribution. (Source: Fieldwork 2024)

About 50.7 % of the respondents were between ages (15-16), followed by those between ages (13 -14) whom constitute 35.6%. Ages 17 and above constitute 12.3 while ages (10 -12) constitute 1.4%. The majority were those within ages (15 -16) this is because of the nature of the school enrolment in the region where Child start secondary education between ages (12-13), by the time they will reach JSS 3 they will be around ages (15-16).

Research Question 1: What is the influence of infrastructural facilities on Academic performance among government junior secondary school students in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?

Table 1: Impact of school Infrastructural Facilities on junior secondary school students' Academic Performance

S/N	Statement	N	X	Rank	SD	Decision
1	Enough classrooms influence academic Performance.	146	3.21*	1	1.47	Agree
2	Equipped school library influences academic Performance.	146	2.76*	2	1.18	Agree
3	Adequate school playground.	146	2.69	3	1.17	Disagree
4	The presence of computers helps students to expand their knowledge and skills.	146	2.56	4	1.17	Disagree
5	Adequacy of Laboratory Equipment in the Schools affect performance.	146	2.30	5	1.08	Disagree

Cumulative Mean: 2.70 (Disagreed)

Results presented in (Table 1) revealed the influence of school infrastructural facilities on academic performance. The variables were as follows; enough classrooms influence academic performance (MS = 3.2) was ranked first. This is because having a conducive place for the students sit down and learn may enhance their ability and concentration for effective academic activities. Equipped school library influences academic Performance (MS =2.7) was ranked second among the infrastructural variables that influence academic performance. This is because after having adequate classrooms where teaching and learning is been taken place, the next place is the library where student use to go and read and master what they learn in the class room. Having adequate school playground (MS = 2.6) was ranked third among the infrastructural component the influence academic performance, having a playing ground make the student to relax and learn some physical activities. The presence of computers helps students to expand their knowledge and skills (MS= 2.5) was ranked fourth among the factors, now a days there are a lot of E-learning materials and programs that aid student academic performance. Adequacy of laboratory equipment in the schools affect performance (MS=2.3) was ranked fifth among the variables, adequacy of those equipment will enhance students'

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knowledge while conducting practical. In summary, Table 3.1 revealed the mean score results on the influence of school infrastructural facilities on academic in performance Dutsin-Ma, where three (3) statement out of five (5) items (3, 4, and 5) had their mean score below the critical mean of 2.70 (2.69, 2.56 and 2.30) and two (2) had their mean score above the critical mean score of 2.70 indicating that the respondent in items (1 and 2).

Research Question 2: What are the instructional facilities influence Students' Academic performance of government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State?

Table 2: Influence of Instructional Materials on Academic Performance

	Statement	N	X	Rank	SD	Decision
6	The use of typewriters as teaching aid help in learning process and academic performance.	146	2.86	4	1.09	Agree
7	Visual aids teaching and learning process and academic performance	146	2.88	3	1.11	Agree
8	Graphics, posters and charts aids influence teaching and learning process and academic performance.	146	3.23	1	1.03	Agree
9	Use of audio aids teaching and learning process and academic performance.	146	2.99	2	1.00	Agree
10	The use of projectors influence teaching and learning process and academic performance.	146	2.45	5	1.23	Disagree
Cumulative Mean:			2.88			Agreed

Table 3.2 revealed the mean score results on Influence of Instructional Materials on Academic Performance in Dutsin-Ma, where one (1) statement out of five (5) items had its mean score below the critical mean of 2.88 (2.45) and four (4) had their mean score above the critical mean score of 2.88 indicating that the respondent in items (6, 7,8 and 9). The use of graphics, posters and charts aids influence teaching and learning process and academic performance (MS: 3.23), Use of audio aids teaching and learning process and academic performance (2.99), visual aids teaching and learning process and academic performance (MS: 2.88), the use of typewriters as teaching aid help in learning process and academic performance (MS: 2.86) were rand (1, 2, 3 and 4) respectively.

Research Question 3: What are the factors influencing the management of school facilities in government junior secondary school Dutsin-Ma LGA?

Table 3: Factors Affecting Management of School Facilities

	Statement	N	X	Rank	SD	Decision
11	Inadequate funding affect management of school Facilities.	146	3.27*	2	1.09	Agree
12	Nature of Schools' physical facility affect its management.	146	3.45*	1	0.97	Agree
13	Lack of equipped laboratory technicians affect its management.	146	3.01*	3	1.166	Agree
14	Political factors management of school Facilities.	146	2.60	5	1.27	Disagree
15	Use of poor-quality components and materials by the maintenance department and contractors.	146	2.99	4	1.26	Disagree
Cumulative Mean:			3.06			Agreed

Results presented in Table 3.3 are the factors affecting management of school facilities. From the Table 3.3, two (2) out of five items were below the critical mean of 3.06. These are items (19 and 20). Political factors management of school Facilities (MS: 2.6) which was ranked fifth, use of poor-quality components and materials by the maintenance department and contractors (MS: 2.99) which was rank forth. While three (3) out of the five items were above the critical mean of 3.06. These include items (16, 17 and 18). Inadequate funding affect management of school facilities (MS: 3.45), lack of equipped

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laboratory technicians affects its management (MS: 3.45), political factors management of school facilities (MS:301) and they were ranked (1st, 2nd and 3rd) respectively. This means that those with mean score above the critical mean have agreed with the statements while those below the critical mean disagreed with those statements.

Discussion of findings

Research question one aimed to investigate the correlation between infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in a government junior secondary school in Dutsin-Ma LGA. The respondents supported the notion that school infrastructural facilities have a substantial impact on students' academic performance. This aligns with the perspective of Davis-Langston (2012), who asserted that the school environment holds the most significant influence on learning and academic performance. In addressing research question two, the study revealed that the use of instructional materials plays a crucial role in influencing student academic performance. The respondents agreed that instructional materials significantly affect students' academic outcomes. Aman's (2021) research supported these findings, emphasizing the notable positive impact of instructional materials on student performance compared to those who did not utilize such resources. Moreover, the study underscored the importance of educational facilities in the teaching and learning process, contributing to improved student retention, assimilation, and overall students' academic performance.

For research question three, the investigation sought to identify the factors influencing the management of school facilities in government Junior Secondary School Dutsin-Ma LGA. The respondents acknowledged that inadequate funding, a lack of equipped laboratory technicians, and political factors are major contributors to the challenges in managing school facilities. Semako (2019) and Mewomo, Ndlovu, and Iyiola (2022) supported these findings, citing factors such as the provision of equipped laboratories, adequate funding, and the condition of physical facilities as significant elements affecting the effective management of public secondary school facilities. Additionally, issues like the availability of funds, occupants' knowledge of facility management, absence of policy guiding facility management practices, the state of deterioration of facilities, design concepts, poor or inadequate funding in education, and economic factors were identified as causes for the improper management of educational facilities. Furthermore, political influence was noted to impact the provision of funding for the management of educational facilities.

Conclusion

This research has delved into the critical relationship between school facilities and students' academic performance in junior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria. The findings underscore the significant influence that well-equipped school facilities have on shaping students' educational outcomes. As educational stakeholders consider strategies for improving academic performance, it is clear that prioritizing the development and maintenance of school facilities should be a central focus. This study contributes valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on enhancing educational quality and effectiveness in the local context, providing a basis for informed decision-making and targeted interventions to benefit the students in junior secondary schools

Recommendation

With reference to the findings from the study, the following recommendation were made;

1. Proper and adequate infrastructural facilities should be provided in the school.
2. Adequate use of instructional materials by the teachers should be encourage.
3. Government should create good school environment for effective learning.
4. Proper funding of educational sector and employing qualified technicians by the government.

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